

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for NEK1 (UniProt ID: Q96PY6) for use in western blot

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Abstract

The serine/threonine kinase NEK1 is a key player in DNA damage response, cell division, and the function of primary cilia and mitochondria. Here we have characterized nine NEK1 commercial antibodies for western blot using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

Q96PY6, *NEK1*, NEK1, Serine/threonine-protein kinase Nek1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

NEK1 is one of the eleven members of the NEK family of serine/threonine kinases involved in cell cycle regulation (1). NEK1 contains an N-terminal conserved catalytic kinase domain and several coiled coil domains responsible for autophosphorylation and activation (2, 3). In addition to its role in mitotic regulation (4, 5), NEK1 responds to early DNA damage (6, 7), and regulates ciliogenesis (8) and mitochondrial function (9). *NEK1* mutations are linked to the polycystic kidney disease (10), an autosomal recessive ciliopathy, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (11) and Mohr-syndrome (12).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (13). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein (13). Here we characterized nine commercial NEK1 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of NEK1 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (14) and in Table 4 of this data note (13).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (15, 16). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (17). HeLa expresses the NEK1 transcript at $2.7 \log_2$ TPM+1 and was modified with CRISPR/Cas9 to KO the corresponding *NEK1* gene (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the HeLa does not carry mutations in the *NEK1* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

To screen all nine by western blot, WT and *NEK1* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the nine antibodies NEK1 antibodies in parallel (Figure 1A). Additionally, the differential expression of NEK1 across a panel of cell lines was investigated by western blot in Figure 1 B using one selected renewable antibody. All cell lines used are listed in Table 1 and the corresponding RNA values are shown in Figure 1B.

In conclusion, we have screened nine NEK1 commercial antibodies in western blot by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HeLa WT and *NEK1* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in western blot (17). High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect NEK1 were identified. Researchers who wish to study NEK1 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available NEK1 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in NEK1, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. NEK1 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (13). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (18, 19). HeLa KO clone corresponding to the *NEK1* was generated with low passage cells following this CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing method: [10.5281/zenodo.3738361](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3738361). Two guide RNAs were used to introduce a STOP codon in the *NEK1* gene (sequence guide 1: GAGACUAGUACAGGCCUGUU, sequence guide 2: AGAAACGCUGGUCCAAAUCC). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

HeLa WT and *NEK1* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of $\sim 0.2 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate

(Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the NEK1 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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References

1. Fry AM, O'Regan L, Sabir SR, Bayliss R. Cell cycle regulation by the NEK family of protein kinases. *J Cell Sci.* 2012;125(Pt 19):4423-33.
2. Chen L, Lu H, Ballout F, El-Rifai W, Chen Z, Gokulan RC, et al. Targeting NEK Kinases in Gastrointestinal Cancers: Insights into Gene Expression, Function, and Inhibitors. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2025;26(5).
3. Surpili MJ, Delben TM, Kobarg J. Identification of proteins that interact with the central coiled-coil region of the human protein kinase NEK1. *Biochemistry.* 2003;42(51):15369-76.
4. O'Regan L, Blot J, Fry AM. Mitotic regulation by NIMA-related kinases. *Cell Div.* 2007;2:25.
5. Chen Y, Chen CF, Chiang HC, Pena M, Polci R, Wei RL, et al. Mutation of NIMA-related kinase 1 (NEK1) leads to chromosome instability. *Mol Cancer.* 2011;10(1):5.
6. Pavan ICB, Peres de Oliveira A, Dias PRF, Basei FL, Issayama LK, Ferezin CC, et al. On Broken Ne(c)ks and Broken DNA: The Role of Human NEKs in the DNA Damage Response. *Cells.* 2021;10(3).
7. Pelegrini AL, Moura DJ, Brenner BL, Ledur PF, Maques GP, Henriques JA, et al. Nek1 silencing slows down DNA repair and blocks DNA damage-induced cell cycle arrest. *Mutagenesis.* 2010;25(5):447-54.
8. White MC, Quarmby LM. The NIMA-family kinase, Nek1 affects the stability of centrosomes and ciliogenesis. *BMC Cell Biol.* 2008;9:29.
9. Chen Y, Craigen WJ, Riley DJ. Nek1 regulates cell death and mitochondrial membrane permeability through phosphorylation of VDAC1. *Cell Cycle.* 2009;8(2):257-67.
10. Upadhy P, Birkenmeier EH, Birkenmeier CS, Barker JE. Mutations in a NIMA-related kinase gene, Nek1, cause pleiotropic effects including a progressive polycystic kidney disease in mice. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2000;97(1):217-21.
11. Kenna KP, van Doormaal PT, Dekker AM, Ticozzi N, Kenna BJ, Diekstra FP, et al. NEK1 variants confer susceptibility to amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Nat Genet.* 2016;48(9):1037-42.
12. Monroe GR, Kappen IF, Stokman MF, Terhal PA, van den Boogaard MH, Savelberg SM, et al. Compound heterozygous NEK1 variants in two siblings with oral-facial-digital syndrome type II (Mohr syndrome). *Eur J Hum Genet.* 2016;24(12):1752-60.
13. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc.* 2024.
14. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
15. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolahdouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife.* 2019;8.
16. Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Schlaifer I, Ayoubi R, Edwards AM, Durcan TM, et al. Identification of highly specific antibodies for Serine/threonine-protein kinase TBK1 for use in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. *F1000Res.* 2022;11:977.
17. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife.* 2023;12.
18. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51(D1):D358-d67.
19. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech.* 2018;29(2):25-38.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CCL-2	CVCL_0030	HeLa	WT
Montreal Neurological Institute, EDDU	-	CVCL_A8DV	HeLa	<i>NEK1</i> KO
ATCC	CRL-2266	CVCL_0019	SH-SY5Y	WT
ATCC	CRL-2142	CVCL_1702	SK-N-FI	WT
ATCC	CCL-247	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
ATCC	CRL-1620	CVCL_0131	A-172	WT
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT

Table 2: Summary of the NEK1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab186519	1000388-5	AB_3698221	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.20	IF
Abcam	ab229489	GR329661-2	AB_2885033	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab241363	1111378-1	AB_3698239	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	IP
GeneTex	GTX130828	42375	AB_2886357	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX638838**	45453	AB_3698343	recombinant mono	HL2488	rabbit	1.00	Wb
GeneTex	GTX638839**	45453	AB_3698344	recombinant mono	HL2489	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	27146-1-AP	54983	AB_2880773	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-54271	VL3152387B	AB_2644600	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.70	Wb, IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-78074	VL3152096D	AB_2736203	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.33	Wb, IP, IF

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot

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Tissue type	Cell line	DepMap RNA score (log2 TPM+1)
Cervical Cancer	HeLa WT	2.8
Neuroblastoma	SH-SY5Y	3.8
Neuroblastoma	SK-N-FI	3.8
Colon/Colorectal Cancer	HCT 116	3.2
Brain Cancer	A-172	3.0
Engineered/haploid	HAP1	3.0
Brain Cancer	U-87 MG	3.0

Figure 1: NEK1 antibody screening by western blot

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: NEK1 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HeLa WT and *NEK1* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated NEK1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab186519 at 1/500, ab229489 at 1/500, ab241363 at 1/1000, GTX130828 at 1/500, GTX638838** at 1/1000, GTX638839** at 1/1000, 27146-1-AP at 1/500, PA5-54271 at 1/1000 and PA5-78074 at 1/500. **B)** Differential expression of NEK1 was evaluated by western blot in various cell lysates from HeLa (WT and NEK1 KO), and WT SH-SY5Y, SK-N-FI, HCT 116, A-172, HAP1, U-87 MG. Anti-NEK1 GTX638839** was used at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 142.8 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.